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International Journal
of Advances in
Engineering &
Scientific Research
(IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 –3607 (Online)
ISSN: 2349 –4824 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-4-aug-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and
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PASSIVE SOLAR DESIGN

Surendra choudhary¹, and Dr.PBL Chaurasia² and Mr.P.N.Mathur³

1. M.Tech Research Scholar
2. Dean Engg. Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur
3. HOD of civil department, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur

*Centre Of Excellence, Solar Energy Research & Utilization,
Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur*

Introduction

Solar energy can be utilized in various ways – to provide electricity, mechanical power, heat and lighting. Passive solar heating and cooling can save substantial electricity bills. Design of a building is very important for tapping passive solar energy. The building and windows are designed in such a way that they carefully balance their energy requirements without additional mechanical equipment. Solar benefits are utilized through windows and pumps, and fans are used minimally.

Passive cooling covers all natural processes and techniques of heat dissipation and modulation without the use of energy. Some authors consider that minor and simple mechanical systems (e.g. pumps and economizers) can be integrated in passive cooling techniques, as long they are used to enhance the effectiveness of the natural cooling process. Such applications are also called 'hybrid cooling systems'. The techniques for passive cooling can be grouped in two main categories:

- **Preventative techniques** that aims to provide protection and/or prevention of external and internal heat gains.
- **Modulation and heat dissipation techniques** allow the building to store and dissipate heat gain through the transfer of heat from heat sinks to the climate. This technique can be the result of thermal mass or natural cooling.

- **Thermal insulation** - Insulation in the building's envelope will decrease the amount of heat transferred by radiation through the facades. This principle applies both to the opaque (walls and roof) and transparent surfaces (windows) of the envelope. Since roofs could be a larger contributor to the interior heat load, especially in lighter constructions (e.g. building and workshops with roof made out of metal structures), providing thermal insulation can effectively decrease heat transfer from the roof.
- **Behavioral and occupancy patterns** - Some building management policies such as limiting the amount of people in a given area of the building can also contribute effectively to the minimization of heat gains inside a building. Building occupants can also contribute to indoor overheating prevention by: shutting off the lights and equipment of unoccupied spaces, operating shading when necessary to reduce solar heat gains through windows, or dress lighter in order to adapt better to the indoor environment by increasing their thermal comfort tolerance.
- **Internal gain control** - More energy-efficient lighting and electronic equipment tend to release less energy thus contributing to less internal heat loads inside the space.

Modulation and heat dissipation techniques

The modulation and heat dissipation techniques rely on natural heat sinks to store and remove the internal heat gains. Examples of natural sinks are night sky, earth soil, and building mass. Therefore passive cooling techniques that use heat sinks can act to either modulate heat gain with thermal mass or dissipate heat through natural cooling strategies.

- **Thermal mass** - Heat gain modulation of an indoor space can be achieved by the proper use of the building's thermal mass as a heat sink. The thermal mass will absorb and store heat during daytime hours and return it to the space at a later time. Thermal mass can be coupled with night ventilation natural cooling strategy if the stored heat that will be delivered to the space during the evening/night is not desirable.
- **Natural cooling** - Natural cooling refers to the use of ventilation or natural heat sinks for heat dissipation from indoor spaces. Natural cooling can be separated into four different categories: cooling and ventilation, radiative cooling, evaporative cooling, and earth coupling.

Ventilation

Ventilation as a natural cooling strategy uses the physical properties of air to remove heat or provide cooling to occupants. In select cases, ventilation can be used to cool the building structure, which subsequently may serve as a heat sink.

- **Cross Ventilation** - The strategy of cross ventilation relies on wind to pass through the building for the purpose of cooling the occupants. Cross ventilation requires openings on two sides of the space, called the inlet and outlet. The sizing and placement of the ventilation inlets and outlets will determine the direction and velocity of cross ventilation through the building. Generally, an equal (or greater) area of outlet openings must also be provided to provide adequate cross ventilation.
- **Stack Ventilation** - Cross ventilation is an effective cooling strategy, however, wind is an unreliable resource. Stack ventilation is an alternative design strategy that relies on the buoyancy of warm air to rise and exit through openings located at ceiling height. Cooler outside area replaces the rising warm air through carefully designed inlets placed near the floor.
- **Night Flush Cooling** - The building structure acts as a sink through the day and absorbs internal heat gains and solar radiation. Heat can be dissipated from the structure by convective heat loss by allowing cooler air to pass through the building at night. The flow of outdoor air can be induced naturally or mechanically. The next day, the building will perform as a heat sink, maintaining indoor temperatures below the outdoor temperature. This strategy is most effective in climates with a large diurnal swing so the typical maximum indoor

temperature is below the outdoor maximum temperature during the hottest months. Thermal mass is a necessary component to dissipate heat at night.

Radiative Cooling

All objects constantly emit and absorb radiant energy. An object will cool by radiation if the net flow is outward, which is the case during the night. At night, the long-wave radiation from the clear sky is less than the long-wave infrared radiation emitted from a building, thus there is a net flow to the sky. Since the roof provides the greatest surface visible to the night sky, designing the roof to act as a radiator is an effective strategy. There are two types of radiative cooling strategies that utilize the roof surface: direct and indirect.

- **Direct Radiant Cooling** - In a building designed to optimize direct radiation cooling, the building roof acts as a heat sink to absorb the daily internal loads. The roof acts as the best heat sink because it is the greatest surface exposed to the night sky. Radiate heat transfer with the night sky will remove heat from the building roof, thus cooling the building structure. Roof ponds are an example of this strategy. The roof pond design became popular with the development of the Sky thermal system designed by Harold Hay in 1977. There are various designs and configurations for the roof pond system but the concept is the same for all designs. The roof uses water, either plastic bags filled with water or an open pond, as the heat sink while a system of movable insulation panels regulate the mode of heating or cooling. During daytime in the summer, the water on the roof is protected from the solar radiation and ambient air temperature by movable insulation, which allows it to serve as a heat sink and absorb, through the ceiling, the heat generated inside. At night, the panels are retracted to allow nocturnal radiation between the roof pond and the night sky, thus removing the stored heat from the day's internal loads. In winter, the process is reversed so that the roof pond is allowed to absorb solar radiation during the day and release it during the night into the space below.
- **Indirect Radiant cooling** - A heat transfer fluid removes heat from the building structure through radiate heat transfer with the night sky. A common design for this strategy involves a plenum between the building roof and the radiator surface. Air is drawn into the building through the plenum, cooled from the radiator, and cools the mass of the building structure. During the day, the building mass acts as a heat sink